

PREPARING FUTURE TEACHERS TO WORK IN A MULTICULTURAL EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT

Atamurodov D.O.

PhD student, Urganch State University

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Abstract. *This article focuses on the issues of independent search for modern methods and ways of forming the culture of international communication in future students, formation of motives and self-development. It is also thought that the culture of inter-ethnic communication has the function of developing students, and also serves to develop their spiritual and moral qualities and vocabulary. This article serves as a methodological resource for the development of tolerance competence of future teachers.*

Keywords: *future teacher, multiculturalism, culture of interethnic communication, school education, tolerance, nationality, society, multiethnicity, Higher pedagogical education.*

It is of particular importance to motivate future students to independently search for modern methods and ways of forming the culture of inter-ethnic communication. Communicative culture allows students to socialize as an opportunity for individual education and self-development. Social is a multifaceted process, each aspect of which is composed of many knowledge, skills and competencies. Communicative culture is an important form of communication and requires a tolerant attitude towards the opinions of others.

Communication culture is manifested in each student and group of students in its own way.

Communication between people is important for their formation and development. As a result of mastering spiritual values, students develop the ability to perform actions with deep thought. The culture of communication regulates mutual relations between people and serves to form the necessary competence to implement these relations based on the requirements of society. As a result, they provide students with the formation of moral qualities necessary for the life of society, and help them master behavioral strategies.

The culture of inter-ethnic communication has the function of developing students, and primarily serves to develop their moral qualities and vocabulary. In the process of international communication, interpersonal relations rise to a new level of quality. The specific content of the culture of inter-ethnic communication is determined according to its objective and subjective description.

It is known that enriching the content of school education is becoming more relevant today than ever. It is especially important to pay attention to the following issues. One of the leading issues is the formation of the culture of interethnic communication among students. Among many existing problems, the problem of forming the culture of inter-ethnic communication among students is gaining leading importance.

Formation of the culture of interethnic communication among students can be effective in the following cases. For this, the student should be fully involved in the educational situation, and his educational activities should be directed to the acquisition of international communication skills. With the help of the teacher, special attention is paid to the students' acquisition of laws, regulations, methods of activity related to interethnic relations. The teacher's knowledge of international relations and professional skills are important in this regard. This knowledge is

integral part of the culture of inter-ethnic communication. In addition, teachers are required to be able to educate students to have an interest in the culture of international communication. For this, future teachers are required to acquire the most necessary pedagogical knowledge.

Today, there are problems in the formation of the culture of inter-ethnic communication among students.

1. Imbalances between the recognition of respect for values, tolerance and inter-ethnic equality in the current Uzbek society and the pedagogical mechanisms of providing knowledge.

2. Lack of development of mechanisms for developing the skills of international tolerance and recognition of values in students.

3. Lack of development of requirements for pedagogical processes aimed at forming the culture of inter-ethnic communication among students;

4. Inadequate presentation of knowledge and topics related to the formation of the culture of inter-ethnic communication among students in the SES and educational programs.

All this serves to form the skills of understanding, accepting and respecting the uniqueness of representatives of other nations. As a result, students develop a sense of respect for the national culture of representatives of other nations. As a result, future teachers will be able to easily master educational technologies aimed at forming a culture of international communication in students in a multicultural educational environment.

The diversity of communication is evident in the example of inter-ethnic communication. With the help of such communication, teachers and students show their relationship to representatives of other nationalities. By understanding the nature of interethnic communication, the essence of the concept of interethnic communication can be clarified.

First of all, inter-ethnic communication is a special need of the society in relation to the active expression of the individual. By knowing and understanding each other, peoples and nations are able to approach their relations with each other from a national point of view. This determines the character of the interaction of a group of people. National directions of communication do not have their own description.

The unique aspects of international communication are clearly manifested on the basis of cooperation between groups of students. The basis of international dialogue is defined by national, universal and common interests. The peculiarity and special essence of inter-ethnic communication is manifested in the activation of inter-ethnic relations. At the same time, inter-ethnic communication serves to clarify hidden aspects between different ethnic groups. Because inter-ethnic communication is a component of the relationship between them. This relationship is manifested primarily at the level of interpersonal relationships. Such an approach serves to clarify the specific aspects of inter-ethnic relations. Because representatives of different nationalities enter into social relations through international communication. This approach does not require people to enter into a relationship without liking each other, using communication as a form of cooperation.

Accordingly, inter-ethnic dialogue is an opportunity for representatives of different nationalities to express their attitude to each other. This relationship between individuals is clearly manifested in the process of inter-ethnic communication. Because representatives of different nationalities work together in the process of daily relations. For example, students of different nationalities participate together in extracurricular pedagogical processes and various activities at school. They play different games and exchange ideas with each other. In this way, they acquire

social experience. They manage to learn interesting facts about each other's cultures and ways of life. In this way, an interest in the cultural wealth of peers who are representatives of other nationalities, respect for it, and a tendency to study its nature are formed. Interest in the culture of representatives of other nations encourages learning about the important aspects of this culture for the whole of humanity. Based on this, it can be said that inter-ethnic communication is a phenomenon that implements inter-ethnic relations, and this relation acquires an interpersonal and socio-cultural character. As a result, there is an opportunity to find a peaceful solution to the conflicts between peoples and nations. Such solutions are achieved on the basis of ensuring humanity, diligence, and activity.

International communication is an important component of relations between representatives of two or more nationalities in all spheres. According to its nature, it is a component of the spiritual life of the society of Uzbekistan. By its nature, it represents the spiritual-ethical, political, aspects of inter-ethnic relations. That is why inter-ethnic communication represents the ideological-political, spiritual-ethical, aesthetic level of a person's worldview. Therefore, it serves to expand the creative possibilities of students representing each nationality and to enrich each other's worldview.

In a word, the culture of inter-ethnic communication is a set of special knowledge, personal qualities and behaviors corresponding to them, which are manifested in the process of interpersonal communication and relationships. Pedagogical skills of teachers are of particular importance in acquiring such qualities quickly without allowing mutual conflicts. That is why it is necessary to pay special attention to finding, sorting, classifying and systematizing certain didactic tools in order to equip future teachers with the knowledge, methods and techniques related to the formation of the culture of inter-ethnic communication among students.

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